

ADAMA SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY UNIVERSITY

SCHOOL OF ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING AND COMPUTING COMPUTER SCIENCE AND ENGINEERING DEPARTMENT

**Postgraduate Regular MSc Program – 1st Year
Research Methodology and Ethics – CSE6402**

ASSIGNMENT – 1

Activity Report – 1

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Identify possible research thematic areas in computing and research topics in each thematic area.

The Computing or in our case the Computer Science and Engineering domain has numerous research thematic areas ranging from the basics of the hardware to the theoretics of artificial intelligence. Some of them are listed as follows:

Architectures, Compiler Optimization, and Embedded Systems

Research in this area explores the design, development, and use of computer architectures and compilers to improve computational efficiency, throughput, and security. Efficiency, throughput, and security of code execution at the machine level is influenced by the machine architectures, the static and dynamic compilation of high-level languages, and use of parallelism and multi-processors. Specific research in this field includes enhancement of computer micro-architectures and compilers to support system security at both the source code and the binary level, leveraging machine learning techniques to improve compilers, using dynamic binary translation and optimization techniques to support system virtualization, and program execution monitoring for optimization, testing, debugging and security. Recent accomplishments include the first learning-based approach to enhance dynamic binary translation for system virtualization, compiler techniques to enhance security and memory performance of modern multicore processors, and various techniques to localize and fix concurrency bugs in parallel programs.

Bioinformatics and Computational Biology

Research in this area explores the use of computational methods to better categorize, visualize, and model biological data and systems. These problems often involve massive, high-dimensional datasets and their solutions draw from many disciplines of computer science including database management, data mining, machine learning, and algorithmic optimization. Research in this group includes algorithms for sequence and structure analysis, protein structure prediction, virtual screening and lead discovery, data modeling of scientific applications, DBMS (database management system) extensions in support of brain image and proteomics analyses and building predictive models for effective disease diagnoses.

Data Science, Data Mining, Databases and Geographical Information Systems

Research in this area explores efficient storage, retrieval, analysis, and visualization of data for analysis and pattern discovery. This encompasses a wide range of topics including improved indexing and query languages, data compression, multimedia storage and retrieval, data clustering, pattern matching, and high-dimensional data modeling. Specific research thrusts in the department include geographical databases, mapping models, anomaly and pattern detection, query processing, and spatial and scientific data mining for application domains like bioinformatics, cyber security, sensor networks, transportation, and the Web. This group has extensive connections with industry and national labs, providing a rich source of problems, datasets, and experience for students.

Graphics and Immersive Computing

Research in this area explores data visualization, non-photorealistic renderings, and perception in virtual environments. It draws from and contributes to work in algorithms, human perception, art, animation, computer vision, and image processing. Specific research thrusts in the department include information visualization, visualization of 2-D and 3-D flow data, multivariate visualization, non-photorealistic rendering, volume visualization, point based modeling and rendering, physically and perceptually based image synthesis, color appearance design and reproduction, and the investigation of perceptual issues in virtual environments.

High Performance Computing

Research in this area explores the development and analysis of parallel algorithms for distributed or multiprocessor systems. These methods are effective for data intensive applications and/or computationally intensive applications such as optimization, graph partitioning, data mining, and solving sparse linear equations. Specific research in this field focuses on grid computing, parallel algorithm design, performance analysis, and sparse matrix algorithms for large-scale scientific and engineering simulations.

Human Computer Interaction (HCI)

Research in this area focuses on developing more effective methods for humans to interact with and use computer technology. HCI draws from computer science, sociology, and psychology to create better interfaces, to improve human-human interactions, and to tailor computer technology to the needs of an individual or organization. The department's HCI group specializes in interfaces that help groups of people work together more effectively. Research efforts include developing algorithms and interfaces for handheld devices to aid coordination in space and time, and in applying social science theories from economics and social psychology to the development of community Web sites.

Networks, Distributed Systems, and Security

Research thrusts broadly include development of innovative theories and techniques, efficient and scalable mechanisms and protocols, and novel network architectures and services. These techniques enhance the availability, reliability, quality-of-service, mobility, manageability, privacy and security for current and future Internet, emerging wireless, sensor, peer-to-peer systems, Grid systems and applications, large-scale storage networks, networked multimedia systems and applications.

Robotics and Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a general term that implies the use of a computer to model and/or replicate intelligent behavior. Research in AI focuses on the development and analysis of algorithms that learn and/or perform intelligent behavior with minimal human intervention. These techniques have been and continue to be applied to a broad range of problems that arise in robotics, e-commerce, medical diagnosis, gaming, mathematics, and military planning and logistics, to name a few. Several research groups fall under the general umbrella of AI in the department, but are disciplines, including robotics, natural language processing (NLP), computer vision, computational biology, and e-commerce.

Specifically, research is being conducted in estimation theory, mobility mechanisms, multi-agent negotiation, natural language interfaces, machine learning, active computer vision, probabilistic language models for use in spoken language interfaces, and the modeling and integration of visual, haptic, auditory, and motor information.

Software Engineering and Programming Languages

Research in this area focuses on the design of new formalisms and frameworks to improve the quality of software. Software is a solution to a computational problem using a formal programming language. The constructs of the language and the tools available to model, implement, and test a software system influence the quality of that solution, in terms of correctness, reliability, readability, computational efficiency, and efficiency in design and development. At the linguistic level, research focuses on constructing methods for extending existing languages with domain specific features, for example, and in exploiting logic and type theory-based approaches in developing flexible and secure programs.

Theoretical Foundations

Research in theoretical foundations formally defines both the types of problems that can be solved using a computer and the quality of their solutions. Computers are limited by space and time. Methods developed in this area define the plausibility of an optimal solution, the quality of the approximate solution, and the resources necessary to find each, thus leading the way to better utilization of a computer's resources or those of multiple computers in parallel. Specific research in this area encompasses a broad range of foundational topics in computer science including computational learning theory, complexity theory, algorithm and data structure design, parallel algorithms, geometric computing, cryptography, computational logic, programming languages theory, and matrix computations.

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- Here at Adama Science and Technology University, the Computer Science and Engineering Department has grouped six Special Interest Groups (SIG) based on a broad specialization computing area, and those are Data Science, Cloud Computing, Network Science, Computer Vision, Cloud Computing, Artificial Intelligence, and Smart Software and Systems. It is quite visible the resemblance from the above list for research thematic areas that these categories are part of one or multi-disciplinary domains mentioned above.
 - Out group is comprised of four members, 3 of which are from the Data Science SIG and one from Smart Software and System SIG. We held discussions in what specific thematic area this research proposal should focus on. After some deliberation, we decided this proposal should steer towards the Data Science world – specifically the Natural Language Processing domain with a real-life use case solving a major problem. But first we were interested in getting the full picture of the Data Science scene and what comes with it.

Data Science

Data science is the domain of study that deals with vast volumes of data using modern tools and techniques to find unseen patterns, derive meaningful insights, and make business decisions. Data science encompasses a set of principles, problem definitions, algorithms, and processes for extracting nonobvious and useful patterns from large data sets.

In fact, the terms data science, machine learning, and data mining are often used interchangeably. The commonality across these disciplines is a focus on improving decision making through the analysis of data. However, although data science borrows from these other fields, it is broader in scope. Machine learning (ML) focuses on the design and evaluation of algorithms for extracting patterns from data. Data mining generally deals with the analysis of structured data and often implies an emphasis on commercial applications. Data science takes all these considerations into account but also takes up other challenges, such as the capturing, cleaning, and transforming of unstructured social media and web data; the use of big data technologies to store and process big, unstructured data sets; and questions related to data ethics and regulation.

Life Cycle of Data Science

Data science's lifecycle consists of five distinct stages, each with its own tasks:

- 1. Capture:** Data Acquisition, Data Entry, Signal Reception, Data Extraction. This stage involves gathering raw structured and unstructured data.
- 2. Maintain:** Data Warehousing, Data Cleansing, Data Staging, Data Processing, and Data Architecture. This stage covers taking the raw data and putting it in a form that can be used.
- 3. Process:** Data Mining, Clustering/Classification, Data Modeling, Data Summarization. Data scientists take the prepared data and examine its patterns, ranges, and biases to determine how useful it will be in predictive analysis.
- 4. Analyze:** Exploratory/Confirmatory, Predictive Analysis, Regression, and Text Mining, Qualitative Analysis. Here is the real meat of the lifecycle. This stage involves performing the various analyses on the data.
- 5. Communicate:** Data Reporting, Data Visualization, Business Intelligence, and Decision Making. In this final step, analysts prepare the analyses in easily readable forms such as charts, graphs, and reports.

Thematic Areas of Research Exploration in Data Science

Some of the research areas in data science are:

- Data Mining

The process of extracting useful patterns from a data set to solve a well-defined problem. Data mining involves the analysis of large sets of data to produce meaningful information. Experts in this specialization apply statistics and predictive models to reveal patterns, trends, and correlations in data. This information can be used to predict future outcomes and to develop business solutions.

- Big Data Analytics

Big data analytics examines large amounts of data to uncover hidden patterns, correlations, and other insights. Recent year's big data has been accumulated in several domains like health care, public administration, retail, biochemistry, and other interdisciplinary scientific research. Big data analytics and data science are becoming the research focal point in industries and academia. Data science aims at researching big data and knowledge extraction from data.

- Data Visualization

Data sets are sometimes hard to understand. Data analysis and data modeling can be complicated tasks, but there are likely better ways to visualize your data in well-organized manner. So, data visualization is a way to represent data that allows people to understand data more easily. Any interested academic personnel in computing can carry out his scientific research on this sub discipline of data science.

- Data warehousing

Data Warehouse is a structured organization of all available data in the company. the main source of information for data scientists are corporate data warehouses. Data scientists rely on data and data infrastructures to do their analytics and modelling. some of applications of data warehousing include banking, finance, education, healthcare, insurance etc.

- Machine learning

The field of ML is at the core of modern data science because it provides algorithms that can automatically analyze large data sets to extract potentially interesting and useful patterns. Machine learning has continued to develop and innovate right up to the present day. Some of the most important developments include ensemble models, where predictions are made using a set (or committee) of models, with each model voting on each query, and deep-learning neural networks, which have multiple (i.e., more than three) layers of neurons.

- Data Engineering

Data engineers build and maintain frameworks that transform data into a format that is useful for analysis. This involves consolidating, cleansing, and structuring data from different sources into a single warehouse.

- Natural Language Processing

Natural Language Processing or NLP is a branch that focuses on teaching computers how to read and interpret the text in the same way as humans do. It is a field that is developing methodologies for filling the gap between Data Science and human languages.

Everything we speak or express holds great information and can be useful in making valuable decisions. But extracting this information is not that easy as humans can use several languages, words, tones, etc. All these data that we are generating through our conversations, tweets, etc. is highly unstructured. The traditional techniques are not capable of extracting insights from this data. But thanks to the advanced technologies like machine learning and NLP that have brought a revolution in the field of Data Science.

Select one research topic, which is of high interest to you.

From the vast research areas discussed above, we selected the Data Science domain specifically the Natural Language Processing branch. As a research topic, we wanted to work on social media data analysis to deal with a great problem of misinformation, disinformation and hate speech across many platforms.

In recent years, online social networking has revolutionized interpersonal communication. The newer research on language analysis in social media has been increasingly focusing on the latter's impact on our daily lives, both on a personal and a professional level. Natural language processing (NLP) is one of the most promising avenues for social media data processing. It is a scientific challenge to develop powerful methods and algorithms which extract relevant information from a large volume of data coming from multiple sources and languages in various formats or in free form. We discuss the challenges in analyzing social media texts in contrast with traditional documents.

Research methods in information extraction, automatic categorization and clustering, automatic summarization and indexing, and statistical machine translation need to be adapted to a new kind of data. The reviews the current research on NLP tools and methods for processing the non-traditional information from social media data that is available in large amounts (big data) and shows how innovative NLP approaches can integrate appropriate linguistic information in various fields such as social media monitoring, healthcare, business intelligence, industry, marketing, and security and defense.

After some deliberation in the group, we decided to work on Hate Speech Detection using some Natural Language Processing technique as a research topic.

A recent study defines hate speech as speech which either promotes acts of violence or creates an environment of prejudice that may eventually result in actual violent acts against a group of people. In the case of Ethiopia, the use of hateful words with an intention to bring about hatred against a group of people based on their ethnicity, political attitude, religion, and socio-economic are prevailing.

Make an Initial Literature Survey (Map a knowledge Domain)

In our preliminary literature survey, we found numerous articles and papers regarding the topic in international, regional, and national scoped; this further strengthened our drive to pursue more in the proposal as it seems a worthy cause for our nation, special in the current climate. A summary of the literature survey is presented as follows.

Hate speech detection related research are done for different language opinionated social media textual content such as English, Chinese, and French using different techniques and approaches are reviewed. Different authors used different techniques such as machine learning, ontology-based approaches, rule-based approaches, sentiment analysis, lexicon-based approaches, feature-selection, cross-validation, and others.

In addition to the techniques, the employed approaches, goals, motivation, domain, target language, dataset source, procedures, experimental results, performance, and challenges are the main points given focus when going through the different works. This proposal introduces sentiment analysis techniques to detect hate speech from Ethiopian indigenous languages particularly Amharic and Oromiffa; which makes it ideal since the contents are mostly of sentimental value or opinion and the speeches are analyzed from social media where sentiment analysis is widely practical upon social media analysis.

After consulting those papers, we generalized that these dimensions of analysis model detection of hate speech into general-feature and specific feature approaches. Approaches from the literature reviews of related works are generalized as follows:

Dictionaries and lexicons: Most of the papers found try to adapt strategies already known in text mining to the specific problem of hate speech detection. The work categorizes the features as the features commonly used in text mining which is dictionaries and lexicons. This approach consists in making a list of words that are searched and counted in the text. In the case of hate speech detection this has been conducted using content words such as insult and swear words, reaction words, and personal pronouns, number of disrespectful words in the text, with a dictionary that consists of words for English language including acronyms and abbreviations, label specific features which consisted in using frequently used forms of verbal abuse as well as widely used stereotypical words.

Bag-of-words (BOW): Another model like dictionaries is the use of bag-of-words. In this case, a corpus is created based on the words that are in the training data, instead of a pre-defined set of words, as in the dictionaries. The disadvantages of this kind of approaches is that the word sequence is ignored, and also, it's syntactic and semantic content. Therefore, it can lead to misclassification if the words are used in different contexts. To overcome this limitation n-grams were implemented. N-grams are one of the most used techniques in hate speech automatic detection and related tasks. In study character n-gram features proved to be more predictive than to Kenn-gram features, for the specific problem of abusive language detection.

Part-of-speech (POS) approaches also make it possible to improve the importance of the context and detect the role of the word in the context of a sentence. These approaches consist in detecting the category of the word, for instance, personal pronoun (PRP), Verb non-third person singular present form (VBP), Adjectives (JJ), Determiners (DT), Verb base forms (VB). Part of speech has also been used in hate speech detection problem even though proved to cause confusion in the class's identification.

Word Embedding: Deep learning techniques are recently being used in text classification and sentiment analysis with high accuracy. One of the approaches of this is word embedding which allows finding both semantic and syntactic relation of words, which permits the capturing of more refined attributes and contextual cues that are inherent in human language.

Formulate the research problem

Hate messages are prevalent and challenging in the Ethiopian online community as individuals spread hate messages hiding behind their screens. The government of Ethiopia oversee and monitor content in social network in a bid to govern hate speech through one-time interruption of the internet service. Research conducted by Amnesty International and the Open Observatory of Network Interference (OONI) between 2018 and 2021 shows that access to WhatsApp, Facebook and others was blocked, as well as at least 16 news outlets. It is an open secret that the recent widespread hate speech and call for violence particularly targets persons of a particular group. It is therefore, of critical importance to monitor and identify instances of hate speech, as soon as possible to prevent their spread and possible unfolding into acts of violence or hate crimes and destroys the lives of individuals, families, communities, and the country.

A recent study defines hate speech as speech which either promotes acts of violence or creates an environment of prejudice that may eventually result in actual violent acts against a group of people. In the case of Ethiopia, the use of hateful words with an intention to bring about hatred against a group of people based on their ethnicity, political attitude, religion, and socio-economic are prevailing.

The anonymity of social networks makes it attractive for hate speech to mask their criminal activities online posing a challenge to the world and in particular Ethiopia. With this ever-increasing volume of social media data, hate speech identification becomes a challenge in aggravating conflict between citizens of nations. The high rate of production, has become difficult to collect, store and analyze such big data using traditional detection methods.

With the advent information age, people are puzzled with vast amount of information from the Internet. Social media is a highly active platform which is challenged with different issues like hate speech and disinformation. Today, social media in Ethiopia is full of turmoil where hate is a concern at every turn and scroll. We can take as an example the incident last month that resulted in the terrible attacks on churches and mosques around the country after a widespread of hate speech around social media that fueled the whole ordeal. People are openly defaming, demeaning, or devaluing others which is inhumane.

Hate speech detection implemented at feature level would create a monitored environment that no hate speech is tolerated and exercised; creating a safe and tolerable web environment where everyone respects and interacts peacefully. Hate speeches that are tagged would be investigated and people exercising it would become accountable for their actions which may create catastrophic results. In the long run, hate-free speech would build societal unity and peace for all people. It is also meant to create awareness about the seriousness of the action and its dangerous outcome.

Formulate the Research Design

The primary research method for this study is literature review and conceptual modeling. Constraint identification and classification through a structured approach is productive way to test out different algorithms that are offered by Sentiment Analysis. This study will first review various types of text analysis to determine and distinguish the structure of hate speech in the model.

A survey of different demography will be commenced to gain a perspective of hate speech from the public with questionnaires, and a sample textual data collection from different social media like Facebook, Telegram from public pages, individual politicians, activists, News pages and various group pages; posts and comments from different timelines will be retrieved to build the corpus. These pages typically post discussions spanning across a variety of political and religious topics. By doing so, authors could capture both casual conversations and politically hated posts and comments. A versatile Facebook crawler, which exploits the Graph API to retrieve the content of the comments from Facebook posts using Facepager would be employed. Facebook is selected to collect data from social media for the following reasons. Facebook is the most important platform for reaching out to online audiences, and especially the youth. Comparative studies have shown how in countries with limited Internet penetration, like Ethiopia, Facebook has become almost a synonym for the Internet, a platform through which users access information, services, and participate in online communications.

A comprehensive model of sentiment analysis using one of the following algorithms: TI-IDF, Naïve-Bayesian, Random Forest, Logistic Regression and also string labeling algorithms like Conditional Random Field (CRF), Model Hidden Markov (HMM), Word2Vec, Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-LSTM) or Entropy. However, we must choose the features manually to bring the model with high accuracy. The model would undergo multiple tests for multiple text samples to classify them accordingly and tag them as efficiently as possible.

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